

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE AND FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Interlaminar fracture behavior of composite materials under static and cyclic loadings has been studied using a width tapered double cantilever beam specimen. The fracture energy is evaluated by compliance, beam and area methods. The comparison results show that the initial fracture energy could be evaluated either by beam or area method while the crack growth resistance could be calculated by compliance method. Increases in the critical load and fracture energy due to fiber bridging are predicted by a power function of fracture area. The interlaminar fatigue crack growth behavior is studied through the constant cyclic strain energy release rate range test. A modification of Paris' power law is made to interpret fatigue crack growth under the influence of fiber bridging. The predicted fatigue life by the modified power law is reasonably close to the experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Failure modes of composite materials are complicated and quite different from those of isotropic materials such as metals. Fiber matrix debonding, fiber fracture, matrix failure and delamination are the main possible failure modes. Among these failure modes, delamination due to interlaminar flaws is peculiar to composite laminates and may occur at ply drop-offs, edges, holes and in the area of impact damage. The replacement of conventional materials by advanced composites is sometimes hindered due to their poor resistance to delamination growth. Therefore, the delamination problem must be understood before safer and more efficient composite structures can be designed. There have been a lot of investigations [1-10] on the delamination behavior of composite materials during the past 15 years. The width tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB) [1-6], double cantilever beam (DCB) [6-9] and tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) [10] are popular specimens for characterizing the opening mode interlaminar fracture toughness. One of the main differences between these specimens is that under constant load, the strain energy release rate, G_I of WTDCB and TDCB is theoretically independent of crack length while that of DCB increases as crack extends. Therefore, when the interlaminar fracture energy, G_{Ic} is measured under displacement control, the critical load-displacement curves of WTDCB and TDCB generally have small fluctuations around mean values (a saw-tooth appearance) [1-3] while that of DCB shows a continual decrease of critical load as the displacement increases [7]. The advantage of WTDCB specimen for static fracture analysis is discussed in reference [1]. In addition, the constant ΔG_I fatigue test can be conducted easily using WTDCB specimen by simple constant load control, while the test is more difficult using a DCB specimen. The constant ΔG_I test might provide other important information since the crack growth rate, da/dN would be constant under a given constant strain release rate range.

In this study, the interlaminar fracture behavior of composite laminates is investigated using a WTDCB specimen. The fracture energy is evaluated by compliance, beam and area methods and comparison results are presented. The interlaminar fatigue crack growth behavior is studied through the constant cyclic strain energy release rate test. The fiber bridging effect on the static and fatigue delamination is studied based on the phenomenological results. The static experimental data are interpreted by a crack growth resistance concept. The fracture energy increase is formulated as a function of fracture area. To predict fatigue crack growth under the influence of fiber bridging, a modification to the Paris' power law is made. Because of the difficulty in mathematical treatments of the area method, crack growth resistance increase and fatigue crack propagation predictions are investigated using only compliance and beam methods.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

E - glass reinforced epoxy resin materials (unidirectional composites type 1002) manufactured by 3M company were used in this study. The WTDCB specimens with a taper of 3 were machined from the 25.4 mm thickness plates with the 0° fiber direction along the length of the specimen in all cases. Specimen configuration and geometry are based on the results in reference[2]. Fig. 1 shows the specimen configuration. The point of load application was established at the intersection of the width taper lines extended as dotted lines by attaching aluminum loading tabs, as shown in fig. 1. Both edges of the specimen were painted with a white typewriter correction fluid to aid visually locating the crack tip. An MTS machine was used for static and fatigue interlaminar fracture testings. Load was monitored by a load cell and load and displacement were recorded by an x-y recorder for static tests. The crack opening displacement is monitored by a sinusoidal wave loading for static fracture tests. At time t, the total displacement becomes $25.4 \sin(4.2 \times 10^{-4} \pi t)$ mm. The fatigue crack propagation tests were performed in a load control using a sinusoidal wave form. The frequency was 1 Hertz which is believed to give a negligible temperature rise during tests. The applied maximum loads were 445, 489, 534 and 578 N and constant minimum load of 89 N was maintained for all tests.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Strain Energy Release Rate

The critical strain energy release rate, G_c is calculated by compliance method[2], linear beam theory[7] and area method[8]. For a WTDCB, G_c can be expressed as follows.

Compliance Method:

$$G_{IC} = k P_C^2 \frac{dC}{d(a^2)} = km_1 P_C^2 \quad (1)$$

Beam Method:

$$G_{IC} = k P_C^2 \frac{dC}{d(a^2)} = \frac{12 P_C^2 k^2}{E_x^b h^3} \quad (2)$$

Area Method:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{k}{a_2^2 - a_1^2} (P_1 \delta_2 - P_2 \delta_1) \quad (3)$$

where,

- C : compliance
- P_C : critical load at which the crack begins to propagate
- m_1 : constant

k : taper of WTDCB
 h : beam height
 E_x^b : effective bending modulus of the beam along the x-axis
 a : crack length
 δ : crack opening displacement

Crack Growth Resistance due to Fiber Bridging

When fiber bridging exists, the critical load and fracture energy increase as the crack extends. In his study, this increase is called the crack growth resistance due to fiber bridging, G_{RB} . The critical load increase could be written as follows:

$$\Delta P_{CB} = P_{CB} - P_{CI} \quad (4)$$

where,

ΔP_{CB} : critical load increase due to fiber bridging
 P_{CB} : measured critical load
 P_{CI} : initial critical load which is not affected by fiber bridging

It is assumed that the critical load increase is a function of the initial crack length, a and the extended crack length, Δa . It is assumed further that ΔP_{CB} could be represented by a power function of the fracture area, i.e.:

$$\Delta P_{CB} = f(a_0, \Delta a) = f(\Delta A) = \alpha (\Delta A)^\beta \quad (5)$$

where, the constants α and β depend on the materials and specimen geometry and ΔA is the increase in fracture area. The crack growth resistance increase could be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta G_{RB} = G_{RB} - G_{IC} \quad (6)$$

where,

ΔG_{RB} : crack growth resistance increase due to fiber bridging
 G_{RB} : measured crack growth resistance
 G_{IC} : initial fracture energy which is not affected by fiber bridging

Substitution of equations (1), (2), (4) and (5) into the above provides the following crack growth resistance increase:

Beam Method:

$$\Delta G_{RB} = \frac{12 k^2}{E_x^b h^3} f \quad (7)$$

Compliance Method:

$$\Delta G_{RB} = k \frac{dC}{d(a^2)} f \quad (8)$$

where,

$$f = \alpha (\Delta A)^\beta [\alpha (\Delta A)^\beta + 2P_{CI}] \quad (9)$$

Fatigue Crack Propagation

The Paris' power law for fatigue crack propagation could be written

$$\frac{da}{dN} = B \Delta G_I^n \quad (10)$$

and

$$\Delta G_I = G_{I_{\max}} - G_{I_{\min}} \quad (11)$$

where,

da/dN : crack growth rate
 B and n : material constants
 ΔG_I : applied cyclic strain energy release rate range under mode I loading
 N : number of cycles

In this study, maximum and minimum loads were maintained constant throughout the tests. In a WTDCB specimen, the constant load control gives the following cyclic strain energy release rate range:

$$\Delta G_I = q (P_{\max}^2 - P_{\min}^2) \quad (12)$$

where,

$$q = \frac{12 k^2}{E_x^b h^3} \quad \text{Beam Method}$$

and

$$q = k \frac{dC}{d(a^2)} \quad \text{Compliance Method}$$

As it can be seen in equation (12), a constant cyclic strain energy release rate range is applied to the specimens throughout the test. According to the Paris' power law, the crack growth rate, da/dN is constant under the constant strain energy release rate range. However, it is observed that due to fiber bridging, the crack growth rate decreases as the crack extends. Therefore, it seems that the following normalized equation might be better than equation (10) when fiber bridging occurs:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = B \left(\frac{\Delta G_I}{G_{RB}(a)} \right)^n \quad (14)$$

For WTDCB specimen under constant applied load range, fatigue life equation can be found as follows:

$$N_2 - N_1 = \frac{1}{B} \int_{a_1}^{a_2} \left\{ \frac{[P_{CI} + \alpha \{(a^2 - a_0^2)/2k\}^\beta]^2}{p_{\max}^2 - p_{\min}^2} \right\}^n da \quad (15)$$

The above equation can be evaluated by simple numerical treatments. It should be noted that it gives the same predictions whether the compliance or beam method is used for the strain energy release rate calculation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is observed that the critical load increases as the crack extends due to the fiber bridging. The typical load-crack opening displacement curve is presented in fig. 2. The initial fracture energy, G_{IC} and crack growth resistance due to fiber bridging are evaluated by beam, compliance and area methods. Crack growth resistance is plotted against increase in crack length, Δa in fig. 3. Among the three calculation methods, the area method does not provide consistent results. The result shows continual increase of crack growth resistance as the crack extends. It is found that the maximum crack growth resistance value is greater than two and half times the initial fracture energy, G_{IC} . The crack growth resistance is predicted by equations (6) to (9). The prediction results are compared with experimental data in fig. 4. The comparison shows that the experimental data can be well predicted by the proposed method.

It is found that the interlaminar crack growth rate, da/dN decreases with number of cycles due to the fiber bridging. The Paris' power law, equation (10) predicts constant crack growth rate under constant cyclic strain energy release rate range which is quite different from the experimental results. Therefore, when fiber bridging exists and as a result, significant delay of crack extension is observed under the constant cyclic strain energy release rate loading, it seems that the equation (14) might be better than Paris' power law in the analysis of the experimental data. Power law fits of the data, using a least square analysis yielded the following relationship:

$$da/dN = 3.59 \times 10^{-5} (\Delta G_I/G_{RB})^{13.5} \quad (16)$$

The above relation and experimental data are presented in fig. 5. It could be seen that the predicted values lie between the experimental band. The fatigue life prediction is made by the equation (15). The prediction results are compared with experimental data in fig. 6. The comparison shows that the fatigue life could be predicted well by the approaches used in this study. As mentioned before, the use of beam or compliance method in evaluation strain energy release rate provides almost the same results because of the normalizing effect in equation (16). The analysis method used in this study could be applied to fatigue crack propagation study of edge notched and center cracked tensile composite materials specimens where crack growth resistance behavior is observed under static loading.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The compliance method provides higher crack growth resistance than the beam method while the area method does not provide consistent results. The crack growth resistance evaluated by the compliance method might be closer to the true value. The true initial fracture energy can be found either by the beam or area methods.
2. The continual crack growth resistance increase is observed due to the fiber bridging. This behavior can be predicted by a power function of fracture area. The comparison shows a close agreement between the prediction and experimental data.
3. It is found that under the constant cyclic strain energy release rate loading, crack growth rate decreases due to the fiber bridging. This behavior could be interpreted by a normalized Paris' power law. The proposed fatigue life prediction method agrees with experimental data. This method could be applied to the other composite materials such as edge notched or center cracked tensile specimens.

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ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN mm

Fig.1 Width Tapered Double Cantilever Beam Specimen; (a) top view, (b) side view (with aluminum loading tabs)

Fig.2 Typical Load-Crack Opening Displacement Curves for a WTDCB Specimen Showing the Influence of Fiber Bridging.

Fig.3 Crack Growth Resistance versus Increase in Crack Length ($a_0=38.1$ mm)

Fig.4 Comparison of Predicted Crack Growth Resistance Increase with Experimental Data

Fig.5 Relationship between Normalized strain Energy Release Rate Range and Interlaminar Crack Growth Rate for WTDCB Specimens (constant strain energy release rate range test)

Fig.6 Interlaminar Crack Length with Fatigue Cycles for WTDCB Specimens (constant strain energy release rate range test)